
MULTI-SCALE REPRESENTATION OF INTEGER SETS: APPLICATION TO PRIME NUMBERS

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ABSTRACT

We propose a multi-scale analysis method for studying arithmetic properties of integer sets, such as primality. Our approach organizes information through a hierarchy of nested sequences, where each level enables a hierarchical expression of the studied property by examining patterns at varying levels of granularity. To illustrate the method, we apply it to prime numbers. While this does not claim any new breakthroughs on this classical problem, the approach allows for analysis of the studied property across large integer sequences and reveals characteristics observable at different scales. By limiting ourselves to the case of prime numbers, we build sequences with values in $0, \dots, 255$, which have the advantage of simplifying the reading, at different scales, of the encoded property. We free ourselves from the numerous digits of large integers by replacing them with small integers between 0 and 255. We have also highlighted, at different scales, histograms composed of at most 256 values. We have observed that for a sufficiently large interval, they all share a same invariant shape, which can be viewed as a characteristic of prime numbers. Each value in the histogram represents the count of a subset of prime numbers. We have proposed an estimation for each value in the histogram and at all scales. We hope that the proposed framework will be useful for investigating arithmetic properties.

Keywords Number theory, prime number, multi-scale analysis

1 Introduction

This article presents a multi-scale representation of natural numbers that enables the analysis of their arithmetic properties at different resolutions. This approach provides a unified framework for simultaneously studying local structures (fine properties of integers) and global structures (general trends).

Multi-scale methods have proven effective across various scientific domains, particularly through multi-resolution analyses based on wavelets [1], whose applications in signal and image processing are well established. In number theory, a multi-scale analysis has been applied to prime numbers [2] linking primes to fractal geometry and numeric accelerators via the Golden Mean. Our method proposes a different scheme from the existing one and applies to the study of general properties of integers. We defend the proposed framework using primality - a field that has seen significant theoretical advances [3, 4, 5]. Our goal is not to compete with these significant results but rather to demonstrate the value of a multi-scale representation for studying arithmetic properties through pattern analysis at different scales.

The presented multi-scale representation allows analysis of integer sets at different resolutions by generating simple integer sequences. In this article, each scale-descriptive sequence is constrained to integers between 0 and 255. Each integer efficiently encodes a given property across large consecutive integers.

To illustrate the multi-scale representation, let us express it through the example of primality in \mathbb{N}^* :

Level 1 (fine granularity) We partition \mathbb{N}^* into blocks of 8 consecutive integers. Each block is encoded in binary (1=prime, 0=composite), then converted to decimal. For example: $(1, 2, \dots, 8) \rightarrow (01101010)_2 = 106$ and $(9, \dots, 16) \rightarrow (00101000)_2 = 40$.

The first terms of this sequence are: 106, 40, 162, 10, 8, 162, 8, 40, 34, 130, ...

Level 2 (intermediate granularity) We aggregate terms from level 1 into blocks of 8, encoding their non-nullity (1 if $\neq 0$, 0 otherwise). For example: $(106, 40, \dots, 40) \rightarrow (11111111)_2 = 255$. A term like $95 = (01011111)_2$ indicates that 6 of the 8 sub-blocks of 64 integers contain at least one prime.

Level 3 (coarse granularity) By iterating the process on level 2, we obtain a macroscopic view. The first 366 terms equal 255, reflecting the high density of primes in these intervals.

As shown in Figure 1, the hierarchy takes the form of a tree, with information growing increasingly refined at lower levels:

- The root node (255) indicates that the first 512 integers contain primes in all 64-integer sub-blocks
- The node 191 at level 2 already reveals a slight irregularity
- The node 40 at level 1 allows precise localization of the primes 227 and 229

Figure 1: Multi-scale tree illustrating three resolution levels. Each node encodes the presence of prime numbers in a specific interval: 512 integers (level 3), 64 integers (level 2) and 8 integers (level 1). The value 40 at level 1 corresponds to integers 225 – 232, of which only 227 and 229 are prime.

Let us now formally describe this multi-scale representation. Let $\{\phi_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ be a family of indicator functions marking a specific arithmetic property at each scale k , where $\phi_k(n) = 1$ if integer n possesses the property at scale k and 0 otherwise. The hierarchical construction is performed via the sequences $(f^{(k)})_{k \geq 0}$ defined recursively by:

$$\begin{aligned}
 f^{(1)}(n) &= \sum_{j=0}^{2^t-1} \phi_0(2^t n + 1 + j) \cdot 2^{2^t-1-j}, \quad n \in \mathbb{N} \\
 f^{(k+1)}(n) &= \sum_{j=0}^{2^t-1} \phi_k(f^{(k)}(2^t n + j)) \cdot 2^{2^t-1-j}, \quad n \in \mathbb{N}
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

In Equation (1), the parameter k represents the scale, while the fixed value $t > 1$ determines the pattern size of 2^t bits. Throughout this article, we set $t = 3$, resulting in patterns comprising 8 positions.

Specifically, the initial level $f^{(0)}$ directly identifies integers satisfying the base property ϕ_0 . The first level $f^{(1)}$ encodes this property in blocks of 8 consecutive integers $P^{(1)}(n) = \{8n + 1, \dots, 8n + 8\}$ via the binary representation $(\phi_0(8n + 1), \dots, \phi_0(8n + 8))$, converted to a decimal integer equal to $f^{(1)}(n)$, sometimes noted $f^{(1)}(P^{(1)}(n))$.

This construction generalizes to higher scales by setting:

$$P_n^{(k)} = \bigcup_{j=0}^7 P_{8n+j}^{(k-1)}, \quad n \in \mathbb{N}, k > 1 \quad (2)$$

Definition 1. We call the 1-pattern the binary representation $(\phi_0(8n+1), \dots, \phi_0(8n+8))$ encoded by $f^{(1)}(n)$. More generally, the k -pattern, $k \geq 2$, is $(\phi_{k-1}(f^{(k-1)}(8n)), \dots, \phi_{k-1}(f^{(k-1)}(8n+7)))$ encoded by the decimal number $f^{(k)}(n)$.

The k -pattern is also denoted $f^{(k)}(P_n^{(k)})$ to emphasize that the value $f^{(k)}(n)$ characterizes the underlying set $P_n^{(k)}$ of 8^k integers.

The multi-scale representation can be considered as a *simplified reading tool for a property in a sequence of integers*, allowing to abstract away from the complexity of the numerous digits that compose the elements of the sequence. Let us illustrate this with the example of primality.

Consider a computer program that takes as input an interval of large integers and returns simplified sequences enabling a quick analysis of the distribution of prime numbers. For this example, we restrict ourselves to two scale levels. Without loss of generality, consider an integer interval of the form $I = [64a + 1, 64b + 64]$, where a and b are integers.

At scale 2, this interval is represented by the sequence $f^{(2)}(a), f^{(2)}(a+1), \dots, f^{(2)}(b)$. This sequence is itself represented at scale 1 by the values $f^{(1)}(8a)$ to $f^{(1)}(8b+7)$. The latter sequence allows us to locate the prime numbers within I .

Let us take a numerical example with the interval $I = [22\,451\,201, 22\,451\,392]$. The information on the prime numbers in the interval I is summarized by the sequences:

- Three elements of the sequence at scale 2: 193, 245, 20.
- The sequence at scale 1: 2, 8, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 128, 8, 2, 2, 32, 0, 10, 0, 130, 0, 0, 0, 128, 0, 32, 0, 0, 128.

The binary decomposition at the scale 2 is

$$\begin{aligned} f^{(2)}(350\,800) &= 193 = (11000001)_2, \\ f^{(2)}(350\,801) &= 245 = (11110101)_2, \\ f^{(2)}(350\,802) &= 20 = (00010100)_2. \end{aligned}$$

It identifies immediately the blocks of 8 consecutive integers in I that contain at least one prime number. The first 1 in the number 193 indicates that the first 8 integers of I contain at least one prime number. A finer analysis is provided by the sequence $f^{(1)}(n)$ at the scale 1. The first element being 2 means that among the first 8 integers of I , the seventh is prime. More precisely, it can be computed as follows:

$$8 \times (8 \times 350\,800) + 7 = 22\,451\,207.$$

Furthermore, the sequences of the multi-scale representation can be seen as a *union of subsequences*, each capturing a specific characteristic. For instance, in the first-level sequence $f^{(1)}(n)$ for prime numbers, we can analyze the constant subsequence $x_i = f^{(1)}(n_i) = 128$, which corresponds to the property that $8n_i + 1$ is prime while $8n_i + 3$, $8n_i + 5$, and $8n_i + 7$ are not. The sequence $f^{(1)}(n)$ described here decomposes into 14 distinct subsequences. We also propose a *mathematical expression to estimate the number of elements in these subsequences* that are less than a given integer m . More generally, we derive expressions for each bin of the histograms at all scales greater than 2. Each histogram bin counts the occurrences of a pattern encoding a particular primality property.

Furthermore, for sufficiently large intervals, we observe that these *histograms consistently exhibit the same invariant shape*. This persistent shape emerges as a characteristic feature of prime numbers. We additionally show how to adapt the multi-scale representation to Mersenne numbers. Other variants of the proposed model can be developed through minor modifications of Equation (1), such as the variant with overlapping partitions.

2 Example 1. Multi-scale Representation of Prime Numbers

We present a hierarchical construction based on the primality of integers. Let \mathcal{P} be the set of prime numbers. The initial level is defined by the indicator function:

$$\phi_0(n) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } n \in \mathcal{P} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

2.1 First Level

The first level $f^{(1)}$ encodes this property in blocks of 8 consecutive integers:

$$f^{(1)}(n) = \sum_{j=0}^7 \phi_0(8n + 1 + j) \cdot 2^{7-j}, \quad n \geq 0 \quad (4)$$

$f^{(1)}(n)$ is an integer between 0 and 255, its binary decomposition is a pattern (1-pattern) that identifies in a sequence of 8 consecutive integers those that are prime and those that are not. The first 49 values of $f^{(1)}(n)$ are organized in a spiral, see Figures 2 and 3. The quick look to the sequence permits to read easily the distribution of the prime numbers. For example 40 means a presence of a twin prime and the others numbers of the pattern are composite. Here is a first observation about the sequence ($f^{(1)}(n)$).

Pattern Restrictions.

Observation 1. *The integer $f^{(1)}(n)$ takes only 14 distinct values:*

$$f^{(1)}(n) \in P_1 \quad (5)$$

$$\text{where } P_1 = \{0, 2, 8, 10, 32, 34, 40, 106, 128, 130, 136, 138, 160, 162\}$$

Proof. The absence of certain patterns is explained by arithmetic constraints. For example, a pattern like $(0, 1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0, 0)_2 = 42$ is impossible because three consecutive odd numbers cannot all be prime (at least one is divisible by 3).

In the rest of the article, we also denote $np_k(f^{(k)}(n))$ the function which counts the number of 1s in the binary representation of $f^{(k)}(n)$.

Distribution of primes per block. The count of primes within a 1-pattern is determined by :

$$np_1(f^{(1)}(n)) = \begin{cases} 0 & f^{(1)}(n) = 0 \\ 1 & f^{(1)}(n) \in \{2, 8, 32, 128\} \\ 2 & f^{(1)}(n) \in \{10, 34, 40, 130, 136, 160\} \\ 3 & f^{(1)}(n) \in \{138, 162\} \\ 4 & f^{(1)}(n) = 106 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Interpretation of the elements of the sequence $f^{(1)}(n)$. The sequence $f^{(1)}(n)$ provides an encoding for a classification of prime numbers into subsets E_t , where $t \in P_1$. Each subset is defined by $\{n \mid f^{(1)}(n) = t\}$. Here are some examples of these subsets E_t :

- $E_2 = \{8n + 7 \mid 8n + 7 \text{ is prime but } 8n + 1, 8n + 3, 8n + 5 \text{ are not}\}$
- $E_{128} = \{8n + 1 \mid 8n + 1 \text{ is prime but } 8n + 3, 8n + 5, 8n + 7 \text{ are not}\}$
- $E_{10} = \{n \mid 8n + 1 \text{ and } 8n + 7 \text{ are prime but } 8n + 3 \text{ and } 8n + 5 \text{ are not}\}$
- $E_{138} = \{n \mid 8n + 1, 8n + 5 \text{ and } 8n + 7 \text{ are prime but } 8n + 3 \text{ is not prime}\}$
- Similarly, we can define the subsets E_t for $t \in \{0, 8, 32, 34, 40, 130, 136, 160, 162\}$

In the rest of the article, the study is conducted using all the files storing the prime numbers less than 982 451 653 which are available at the website *The first fifty million primes* originally created by Chris Caldwell [6, 7]. Thus, our study is done over the interval $[1, N_{\max}]$, where $N_{\max} = 982\,451\,200$.

Figure 2: Spiral arrangement of sequence elements

34	0	8	10	130	32	128
136	32	2	128	40	138	130
0	160	8	10	162	128	40
32	10	162	106	40	32	2
0	8	8	40	34	130	32
32	34	8	40	2	138	0
128	40	130	2	8	34	8

Figure 3: First 49 elements of the sequence $f^{(1)}(n)$ arranged in a spiral.

158	223	157	182	239	254	83
246	221	251	111	182	183	239
220	253	251	191	255	255	122
159	255	127	255	255	239	243
59	237	255	255	95	254	157
111	252	58	255	123	253	249
247	222	189	189	115	223	238

Figure 4: First 49 elements of the sequence $f^{(2)}(n)$ arranged in a spiral.

255	255	255	255	255	255	255
255	255	255	255	255	255	255
255	255	255	255	255	255	255
255	255	255	255	255	255	255
255	255	255	255	255	255	255
255	255	255	255	255	255	255
255	255	255	255	255	255	255

Figure 5: $f^{(3)}(n)$ defined in Example 1 is constant up to $n = 366$

n	$\pi_{N_{\max}}^{(1)}(n)$	n	$\pi_{N_{\max}}^{(1)}(n)$
0	78 517 574	106	1
2	9 316 943	128	9 314 958
8	10 066 986	130	1 497 811
10	748 618	136	749 060
32	10 065 624	138	93 887
34	749 468	160	750 314
40	842 208	162	92 948

Table 1: Prime numbers: Histogram $\pi_{N_{\max}}^{(1)}(n)$ of 1-patterns

Configuration Type	Proportion
Blocks without primes	63.94%
Blocks with 1 prime	31.56%
Blocks with 2 primes	4.35%
Blocks with 3-4 primes	0.15%

Table 2: Prime numbers: Distribution of 1-patterns

Counting 1-patterns. The statistical distribution of sequence $f^{(1)}(n)$ is presented in Tables 1 and 2. Over the interval $[1, m]$, this distribution is represented by the discrete finite histogram:

$$\pi_m^{(1)}(c) = \begin{cases} \text{card}\{n \in [0, \frac{m}{8}] \mid f^{(1)}(n) = c\} & \text{if } c \in P_1 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Statistically, we observe that the number of empty 1-patterns increases more rapidly than that of 1-patterns containing a single prime number, the latter growing slowly. Moreover, the number of 1-patterns containing 2 or 3 prime numbers decreases as m increases. Tables 2 shows this distribution for $m = N_{\max}$.

Mathematical expressions for the number of 1-patterns. Below, we propose an expression estimating these statistics:

Observation 2.

- Over the interval $[1, m]$, the probability of an odd number being prime is approximately $p(m) = \frac{2\text{li}(m)}{m}$. Thus, numbers in $\{8n + i \mid i = 1, 3, 5, 7\}$ encoded by $f^{(1)}(n)$, with $n \leq \frac{m}{8}$, have the same probability $p(m)$ of being prime.

$$\text{li}(x) = \int_0^x \frac{1}{\ln(t)} dt \quad (7)$$

- The histogram $\pi_m^{(1)}(j)$ can be expressed as follows:

$$\pi_m^{(1)}(j) \approx \begin{cases} C_0^{(1)}(m) \frac{m}{8} (1-p(m))^4 & \text{if } j = 0 \\ C_j^{(1)}(m) \frac{m}{8} p(m) (1-p(m))^3 & \text{for } j \in \{2, 8, 32, 128\} \\ C_j^{(1)}(m) \frac{m}{8} (p(m))^2 (1-p(m))^2 & \text{for } j \in \{10, 34, 40, 130, 136, 160\} \\ C_j^{(1)}(m) \frac{m}{8} (p(m))^3 (1-p(m)) & \text{for } j \in \{138, 162\} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where, for values $m \in [1, N_{\max}]$, $C_j^{(1)}(m) < 2$.

- Consequently, we believe that:

$$\begin{cases} \pi_m^{(1)}(0) < \frac{m}{4} (1-p(m))^4 \\ \pi_m^{(1)}(j) < \frac{m}{4} p(m) (1-p(m))^3 & \text{for } j \in \{2, 8, 32, 128\} \\ \pi_m^{(1)}(j) < \frac{m}{4} (p(m))^2 (1-p(m))^2 & \text{for } j \in \{10, 34, 40, 130, 136, 160\} \\ \pi_m^{(1)}(j) < \frac{m}{4} (p(m))^3 (1-p(m)) & \text{for } j \in \{138, 162\} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Justifications. Empirically, we verify that the probability of an odd number less than m being prime is uniform and thus constant, equal to $\frac{\pi(m)}{m/2} = \frac{2\pi(m)}{m} \approx \frac{2\text{li}(m)}{m}$. Thus, if $(b_7 b_6 \dots b_0)$ is the binary representation of $f^{(1)}(n)$ with $n \leq \frac{m}{8}$, then the probability that $b_i = 1$ (in other words, that $8n + 8 - i$ is prime) is given by $p_i^{(1)}(m) \approx \frac{2\text{li}(m)}{m}$, for $i \in \{1, 3, 5, 7\}$. This observation is empirically verified for values $m < N_{\max}$. Table (6a) shows the deviations between $p_i^{(1)}(m)$ and the approximation $\frac{2\text{li}(m)}{m}$.

To establish the formulas in Equation (8), let's take the example of $\pi_m^{(1)}(j)$ with $j \in \{2, 8, 32, 128\}$. The same reasoning applies to other cases. Consider the case $j = 2$ where the 1-pattern $f^{(1)}(n) = j$ corresponds to $8n + 7$ being prime while $8n + 1$, $8n + 3$ and $8n + 5$ are not, for $n \leq \frac{m}{8}$. Assuming independence, the probability that $8n + 7$ is the only prime number in the sequence is:

$$p(m)(1-p(m))^3$$

This formula remains valid for $j \in \{2, 8, 32, 128\}$.

In the interval $[1, m]$, the number of 1-patterns is approximately equal to $\frac{m}{8}$, so the count $\pi_m^{(1)}(j)$ can be written as:

$$\pi_m^{(1)}(j) \approx \frac{m}{8} p(m) (1-p(m))^3$$

To correct the approximations and the independence assumption, we introduce a correction function $C_j^{(1)}(m)$:

$$\pi_m^{(1)}(j) \approx C_j^{(1)}(m) \frac{m}{8} p(m) (1-p(m))^3$$

The other formulas in Equation (8) are obtained through analogous reasoning.

Furthermore, our experiments show that the $C_j^{(1)}$ is less than 2 and for values $m > 16\,777\,216$, $C_j^{(1)}$ lie always within the interval $[\frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{2}]$. Moreover, we have observed symmetries between patterns, expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} C_2^{(1)}(m) &\approx C_{128}^{(1)}(m), \\ C_8^{(1)}(m) &\approx C_{32}^{(1)}(m), \\ C_{138}^{(1)}(m) &\approx C_{162}^{(1)}(m). \end{aligned}$$

The differences between these coefficients are less than 10^{-2} . This symmetry extends to other patterns, but with errors on the order of 10^{-1} for certain values of m . This is the case for the values of $C_{10}^{(1)}(m)$ and $C_{136}^{(1)}(m)$, as well as those of $C_{34}^{(1)}(m)$ and $C_{160}^{(1)}(m)$.

The formal determination of the coefficients $C_2^{(1)}(m)$ may be the subject of future work.

i	$p_i^{(1)}(m)$	$ p_i^{(1)}(m) - p(m) $	i	$p_i^{(2)}(m)$	$ p_i^{(2)}(m) - q_1(m) $	i	$p_i^{(3)}(m)$	$ p_i^{(3)}(m) - q_2(m) $
1	0.101778	1.251106×10^{-5}	0	0.360642	0.011536	0	0.978058	0.010275
3	0.101790	3.954332×10^{-7}	1	0.360688	0.011583	1	0.978118	0.010335
5	0.101792	1.999584×10^{-6}	2	0.360606	0.011500	2	0.978108	0.010325
7	0.101783	6.827317×10^{-6}	3	0.360629	0.011523	3	0.978279	0.010496
			4	0.360581	0.011475	4	0.978218	0.010435
			5	0.360673	0.011568	5	0.978190	0.010407
			6	0.360627	0.011522	6	0.978243	0.010460
			7	0.360666	0.011561	7	0.978213	0.010430

(a) $m = N_{\max}, p(m) = 0.10179$ (b) $m = N_{\max}, q_1(m) = 0.349105$ (c) $m = N_{\max}, q_2(m) = 0.967783$

Figure 6: Over the interval $[1, N_{\max}]$, the probabilities $p_i^{(k)}$ of observing a '1' at digit position b_i in the binary representation of k -patterns ($k = 1, 2, 3$). The differences between empirical and theoretical probabilities are also shown.

Distance between two identical 1-patterns. Figure 7 shows some statistics computed over the interval $[1, N_{\max}]$, concerning the distance between two consecutive numbers n_1 and n_2 such that $f^{(1)}(n_1) = f^{(1)}(n_2)$.

Let $j \in P_1$ be a 1-pattern; sorting the set $\{n \mid f^{(1)}(n) = j, n = 0, \dots, \frac{N_{\max}}{8}\}$ gives an ordered sequence $n_0^{(j)} < n_1^{(j)} < \dots < n_{s_j}^{(j)}$. The sequence of gaps between two consecutive occurrences of pattern j is defined by $e_i^{(j)} = n_{i+1}^{(j)} - n_i^{(j)}$. The minimum, maximum, mean, and standard deviation of the finite sequence $(e_i^{(j)})_i$ are shown in Figure 7.

(a) Statistics of 1-pattern containing 1 prime number					(b) Statistics of 1-pattern containing 2 prime numbers				
n	Min	Max	Avg	Std	n	Min	Max	Avg	Std
2	1	178	13.18	11.85	10	3	2 097	164.04	158.47
128	1	207	13.18	11.85	34	3	2 400	163.86	158.33
8	1	175	12.20	10.90	40	3	2 028	145.81	140.37
32	1	182	12.20	10.89	130	1	1 289	81.99	79.31
					136	3	2 175	163.95	157.83
					160	3	2 541	163.67	157.84

(c) Statistics of 1-pattern containing 3 prime numbers				
n	Min	Max	Avg	Std
138	3	17 565	1 308.03	1 316.68
162	3	15 828	1 321.21	1 325.35

Figure 7: Statistical summary of the sequences $(e^{(j)})$, $j \in P_1$

2.2 Second Level

To define the second level, we introduce the function ϕ_1 . In this example, ϕ_1 is the indicator function of the presence of at least one prime number in a 1-pattern:

$$\phi_1(n) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } n \in P_1 - \{0\} \\ 0 & n = 0 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

The function ϕ_1 allows us to observe the density and distribution of prime numbers in blocks of 64 consecutive integers. The second level of this multi-scale representation is then defined by:

$$f^{(2)}(n) = \sum_{j=0}^7 \phi_1 \left(f^{(1)}(8n+j) \right) \cdot 2^{7-j}, \quad n \in \mathbb{N} \quad (11)$$

The sequence $f^{(2)}(n)$ takes all values between 0 and 255. The first observed values are: 255, 255, 255, 191, 251, 127, 255. The first 49 values of this sequence are organized in a spiral and represented in Figure 4.

Mathematical estimation of the 2-patterns histogram.

Observation 3.

- (1) Over the interval $[1, m]$, the probability that a 1-pattern contains at least one prime number is approximately equal to

$$q_1(m) = 1 - (1 - p(m))^4$$

- (2) The histogram $\pi_m^{(2)}(n)$ is approximately given by:

$$\pi_m^{(2)}(n) \approx C_j^{(2)}(m) \frac{m}{64} q_1(m)^j (1 - q_1(m))^{8-j}$$

$$\text{where } np_2(n) = j$$

- (3) Empirically, we observe that for $m \in [4\,096\,000, N_{\max}]$, $C_j^{(2)}(m) < 2$.

Justification of (1). A 1-pattern contains 4 odd numbers $8n+1$, $8n+3$, $8n+5$ and $8n+7$. The probability that none of these numbers is prime is $(1 - p(m))^4$. Therefore, the probability that a 1-pattern contains at least 1 prime number is $1 - (1 - p(m))^4$.

Justification of (2). The number of 2-patterns in $[1, m]$ is approximately equal to $\frac{m}{64}$. The probability of having exactly j 1-patterns, containing at least one prime, in a 2-pattern is $q_1(m)^j (1 - q_1(m))^{8-j}$. Using these elements and correcting for the independence assumption and approximation differences, we write:

$$\pi_m^{(2)}(n) \approx C_j^{(2)}(m) \frac{m}{64} q_1(m)^j (1 - q_1(m))^{8-j}$$

The Invariance Shape of the k -Patterns Histogram. The distribution of the sequence $f^{(2)}(n)$ for integers in $[1, N_{\max}]$ is shown in Figure 8a, whereas Figure 8b illustrates the histogram obtained using the model given by Observation 3. The histogram reveals an irregular but repeating shape. The observed periodicity stems from the statistical predominance of 2-patterns with $np_2(f^{(2)}(n)) = 1$ over those with $np_2(f^{(2)}(n)) = 2$, and so forth. The characteristic shape of the histogram becomes clearly apparent for $m > 16000000$.

We conjecture that for a sufficiently large interval, the shape illustrated by Figure 8 holds for every histogram of the sequence $f^{(k)}(n)$ with $k \geq 2$, and remains invariant as the interval size increases. This assertion is based on the study of the histogram estimation of $f^{(k)}(n)$ described in Observation 4.

(a) Histogram of $f^{(2)}$ values

(b) Theoretical histogram with $C_j^{(2)} = 1$ (Cf. observation 3)

Figure 8: Shapes of empirical and theoretical histograms for $f^{(2)}$, computed over $[1, N_{\max}]$.

2.3 Third Level

The hierarchical construction continues to the third level with:

$$f^{(3)}(n) = \sum_{j=0}^7 \phi_2(f^{(2)}(8n + j)) \cdot 2^{7-j}, \quad n \in \mathbb{N} \quad (12)$$

where the filtering function ϕ_2 is defined by:

$$\phi_2(n) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } n \neq 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

This function ϕ_2 indicates the presence of at least one prime number in sequences of 512 consecutive integers.

Pattern restrictions. Over the interval $[1, N_{\max}]$, only 114 distinct values are observed among the 256 possible:

$$f^{(3)}(n) \in \{31, 45, 47, 51, 54, 55, 58, 59, 61, 62, 63, 70, 71, 77, 78, 79, 83, 85, 86, 87, \\ 89, 90, 91, 93, 94, 95, 103, 107, 109, 110, 111, 115, 117, 118, 119, 121 \text{ to } 127, \\ 142, 143, 151, 155 \text{ to } 159, 165, 167, 169 \text{ to } 175, 179 \text{ to } 183, 185 \text{ to } 191, 197, 199, \\ 203, 205, 206, 207, 211, 213, 214, 215, 217 \text{ to } 223, 226, 227, 229, 230, 231, 233 \text{ to } 239, 241 \text{ to } 255\}$$

The histogram of the 3-patterns $f^{(3)}(n)$, for $n \in [0, \frac{N_{\max}}{512}]$, is given in Table 3. We observe that the value 255 represent 83.78%, all these 3-patterns contain at least 8 prime numbers. The sequence $f^{(3)}(n)$ remains constant at 255 for all $n \leq 366$, with first deviation at $f^{(3)}(367) = 223$. Other observations are presented hereafter.

n	$\pi_{N_{\max}}^{(3)}(n)$										
31	15	45	1	47	17	51	1	54	1	55	20
58	2	59	17	61	15	62	10	63	649	70	1
71	1	77	4	78	2	79	8	83	3	85	1
86	1	87	17	89	1	90	1	91	13	93	18
94	17	95	830	103	18	107	23	109	13	110	20
111	761	115	20	117	26	118	15	119	798	121	15
122	14	123	820	124	14	125	837	126	868	127	35878
142	1	143	13	151	9	155	12	156	1	157	16
158	20	159	709	165	1	167	17	169	1	170	1
171	15	172	1	173	18	174	22	175	788	179	15
181	24	182	19	183	804	185	11	186	22	187	824
188	19	189	824	190	798	191	35995	197	1	199	10
203	14	205	20	206	21	207	704	211	21	213	12
214	21	215	763	217	14	218	16	219	832	220	14
221	792	222	835	223	36046	226	1	227	13	229	16
230	12	231	715	233	20	234	22	235	832	236	15
237	845	238	835	239	35953	241	14	242	9	243	699
244	23	245	771	246	775	247	35991	248	8	249	708
250	784	251	36169	252	671	253	36182	254	36171	255	1607654

Table 3: Histogram $\pi_{N_{\max}}^{(3)}(n)$ of 3-patterns

Estimation of the number of k -patterns. Using reasoning similar to that of Observation 3, we can derive estimates at any scale k . Therefore, we obtain the following expression.

Observations 4.

(1) The probability that a k -pattern, $k > 1$ contains at least one prime number is approximately equal to

$$q_k(m) = 1 - (1 - q_{k-1}(m))^8 = 1 - (1 - p(m))^{4 \times 8^{k-1}}$$

(2) The histogram $\pi_m^{(k)}(n)$ is approximately given by:

$$\pi_m^{(k)}(n) \approx C_j^{(k)}(m) \frac{m}{8^k} q_{k-1}(m)^j (1 - q_{k-1}(m))^{8-j}$$

where $np_k(n) = j$

Justification.

(1) Consider a k -pattern $P_n^{(k)} = \bigcup_{j=0}^7 P_{8n+j}^{(k-1)}$. The probability that none of the $P_{8n+j}^{(k-1)}$, $j = 0, \dots, 7$, contains any prime number is $(1 - q_{k-1}(m))^8$. By recurrence, we can write $(1 - q_{k-1}(m))^8 = (1 - p(m))^{4 \times 8^{k-1}}$. Therefore, the probability that at least one of the blocks $P_{8n+j}^{(k-1)}$ contains at least one prime number is

$$1 - (1 - q_{k-1}(m))^8$$

(2) The number $\pi_m^{(k)}(n)$ of k -patterns in $[1, m]$ can be expressed in function of $q_{k-1}(m)$, as we have done for the numbers $\pi_m^{(2)}(n)$ in Observation 3.

Density of prime numbers at the level k . To analyze the sequences $f^{(k)}(n)$, we are interested in the density of prime numbers in a regular partition of \mathbb{N} , although it has been proven that there is no regular partition in which each part contains at least one prime number [8]. In this context, let us define the density as follows:

Definition 2. The prime numbers are said to be dense in $[1, m]$, via the partition $P^{(k)}(n)$, if for all n , the intersection $(P^{(k)}(n) \cap [1, m]) \cap \mathcal{P}$ is non-empty.

Observation 5. For $m > e^{8^k}$, the prime numbers are not dense in $[1, m]$ via the partition $P^{(k)}$.

Indeed, we know that $\text{card}(P^{(k)}(n)) = 8^k$, and that the number of prime numbers in $[1, m]$ is given by $\pi(m) \approx \frac{m}{\ln(m)}$. For the prime numbers to be dense in $[1, m]$ via $P^{(k)}$, the interval must contain at least $\frac{m}{8^k}$ prime numbers. However, if

$$\pi(m) \approx \frac{m}{\ln(m)} < \frac{m}{8^k},$$

then the prime numbers cannot be dense. This inequality is satisfied when $m > e^{8^k}$.

The prime numbers are dense in $[1, N_{\max}]$ under the partition $P^{(3)}$, since $f^{(3)}(n) \neq 0$ for all $n \leq \frac{N_{\max}}{512}$. However, the existence of n such that $f^{(3)}(n) = 0$ is guaranteed for some interval $[1, m]$ with $m > e^{512}$ by density arguments. This upper bound appears excessively large. To find a smaller $m < e^{512}$ such that \mathcal{P} is not dense in $[1, m]$ under $P^{(3)}$, we may solve the inequality $\pi_m^{(3)}(0) > 1$. Using the estimate for $\pi_m^{(3)}(0)$, we obtain:

$$C_j^{(3)}(m) \frac{m}{8^3} (1 - q_2(m))^8 > 1.$$

Since $C_j^{(3)}(m)$ is unknown at this stage, we set it to 1 and empirically search for the smallest m satisfying:

$$\frac{m}{8^3} (1 - q_2(m))^8 > 1.$$

For $m = e^{27}$, this expression evaluates to 1.27. Thus, we hypothesize that the density of \mathcal{P} under $P^{(3)}$ breaks down around $m = e^{27}$.

3 Reconstruction Algorithm

We present an algorithm to reconstruct the integer sequence of \mathbb{N}^* encoded by a 3-pattern C , based on an inverse hierarchical decomposition of patterns. Let D2B be the function that maps any integer n to the set of positions of the value 1 in its 8-bit binary representation:

$$\text{D2B}(n) = \left\{ j \in \{0, \dots, 7\} \mid \left\lfloor \frac{n}{2^{7-j}} \right\rfloor \bmod 2 = 1 \right\}$$

The algorithm begins by identifying positions n satisfying $f^{(3)}(n) = C$ and constructing the list $L3 = \text{D2B}(C)$. For each such n and for each $j \in L3$, it then computes $L2 = \text{D2B}(f^{(2)}(8n + j))$. Next, for each $i \in L2$, it determines $L1 = \text{D2B}(f^{(2)}(8(8n + j) + i))$. Finally, for each $p \in L1$, the numbers satisfying properties ϕ_1 and ϕ_0 represented by C are generated by the sequence $8(8(8n + j) + i) + 1 + p$. The algorithm is summarized below.

Algorithm 1 Reconstruction of integers from a 3-pattern

Require: pattern3, pattern2, pattern1 : lists of patterns for N blocks

Require: C : 3-pattern to decode

Ensure: List of prime integers encoded by C

```

1: Initialize Prime_List  $\leftarrow \emptyset$ 
2:  $L \leftarrow \{n \in \{0, \dots, \lfloor N/512 \rfloor\} \mid \text{pattern3}[n] = C\}$ 
3: for all  $n \in L$  do ▷ Traverse level 3 blocks
4:    $L_3 \leftarrow \text{D2B}(C)$ 
5:   for all  $j \in L_3$  do ▷ Level 2 decomposition
6:      $m \leftarrow 8n + j$ 
7:      $L_2 \leftarrow \text{D2B}(\text{pattern2}[m])$ 
8:     for all  $i \in L_2$  do ▷ Level 1 decomposition
9:        $k \leftarrow 8m + i$ 
10:       $L_1 \leftarrow \text{D2B}(\text{pattern1}[k])$ 
11:      for all  $p \in L_1$  do ▷ Prime number extraction
12:        Prime_List  $\leftarrow$  Prime_List  $\cup \{8k + p + 1\}$ 
13:      end for
14:    end for
15:  end for
16: end for
17: return Prime_List

```

4 Multi-scale Representation of Mersenne primes

We adapt our multi-scale framework to study Mersenne primes, focusing on integers from the set $\mathcal{M} = \{2^{2m+1} - j \mid j = 0, \dots, 7 \text{ and } m \geq 3\}$.

4.1 First Level: Identifying Mersenne primes

The initial level retains the same definition as in previous examples: The indicator function remains:

$$f^{(0)}(n) = \phi_0(n) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } n \text{ is prime} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

For Mersenne primes, the first level specializes to:

$$f^{(1)}(2^{2m+1}) = \sum_{j=0}^7 \phi_0(2^{2m+1} - 7 + j) 2^{7-j}, \quad m \geq 1. \quad (14)$$

Pattern restrictions. A block contains a Mersenne prime if and only if:

$$f^{(1)}(2^{2m+1}) \in \{2, 10, 34, 42, 130, 106, 138, 162\}$$

1-Pattern histogram. For $M = 1000$ ($1 < m \leq M$), the pattern occurrences are summarized in Table 4

1-Pattern distribution. For $1 < m \leq M$, the patterns achieved by $f^{(1)}(2^{2m+1})$ are summarized in Table 5.

Observations 6. For $1 < m \leq M$

1. Only five non-zero patterns appear: $\{2, 8, 10, 42, 128\}$.

Pattern	Occurrences
0	1968
2	15
8	9
10	1
42	1
128	6

Table 4: Distribution of 1-patterns for Mersenne numbers

$f^{(1)}(2^k)$	Values of $k = 2m + 1$
2	7, 13, 17, 19, 31, 61, 89, 107, 127, 251, 607, 1279, 2203, 2281, 3217
8	9, 29, 213, 221, 233, 545, 689, 2321, 3237
10	5
42	3
128	39, 715, 1983, 2319, 2499, 3775

Table 5: Values of $f^{(1)}(2^k)$ for different exponents $k = 2m + 1$

2. No pattern contains more than one prime number for $m \geq 3$.
3. For $m \geq 3$, the identified primes are exclusively of the form:
 - $2^{2m+1} - 1$ (15 cases)
 - $2^{2m+1} - 3$ (9 cases)
 - $2^{2m+1} - 7$ (6 cases)
4. No prime of the form $2^{2m+1} - 5$ is observed.
5. When $2^{2m+1} - 1$ is prime, none of the numbers $2^{2m+1} - 3, 2^{2m+1} - 5, 2^{2m+1} - 7$ are prime (true for $m \geq 5$).

4.2 Second Level

We define the filter for the second level:

$$\phi_1(n) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } n \in \{2, 10, 34, 42, 106, 130, 138, 162\} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

ϕ_1 identifies 2-patterns that contain at least 1 Mersenne prime.

The level 2 construction becomes:

$$f^{(2)}(2^{16m+3}) = \sum_{j=0}^7 \phi_1(f^{(1)}(2^{16m+3+2j})) \cdot 2^{7-j} \quad (16)$$

Recall that in this context a 2-pattern $f^{(2)}(2^{16m+3})$ encodes a sequence of 64 consecutive integers in \mathcal{M} .

2-Pattern distribution. For $m \leq 500$, the patterns achieved by $f^{(2)}(2^{16m+3})$ are summarized in Table 6:

Observations 7. For $0 \leq m \leq 500$, we note:

- Only 14 non-empty blocks of size 64 out of 501.
- Each non-empty block of 64 consecutive integers in \mathcal{M} contains at most one Mersenne prime ($m > 1$).
- Almost all blocks (97.2%) contain no Mersenne primes.

The fact that no 2-pattern contains more than one Mersenne prime empirically confirms their extreme rarity. Among questions worth exploring: the possible existence of unobserved patterns and theoretical study of these multi-scale representation properties.

Pattern $f^{(2)}(2^k)$	Values of $k = 16m + 3$
1	3203
2	115; 595; 1267
4	51; 4243
8	99; 2195
16	83; 515; 2275
32	4419
130	19
229	3
0	otherwise

Table 6: Values of $f^{(2)}(2^k)$ for different exponents $k = 16m + 3$

5 Conclusion

This work explores a multi-scale approach to studying arithmetic properties of natural numbers. Through two examples, prime numbers and Mersenne numbers, we show how this hierarchical representation can reveal interesting structures in the distribution of integers.

The main aspects of this method include encoding arithmetic properties into nested sequences, enabling the simultaneous analysis of both local and global behaviors.

In this article, the generated sequences take integer values between 0 and 255. The predominance of small values in these sequences facilitates a clear interpretation of prime number distributions across intervals of large integers. We further analyze these distributions through scale-dependent histograms, each comprising at most 256 bins. Every bin counts occurrences of specific patterns that encode primality properties. We derive a mathematical expression to estimate the bin counts in these histograms. For sufficiently large intervals, empirical results strongly suggest that these histograms approach a same invariant form. This persistent structure appears to be an intrinsic characteristic of prime number distributions.

Future research directions may include refining the proposed mathematical estimates for histogram bins, exploring multi-scale representations with overlapping pattern schemes, and adapting the method to variable pattern sizes.

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